

Exploring an Environmental Water Manager for the Sacramento River System

EDF & Cornell University Workshop | July 18, 2024

Welcome!

Let's start off by getting to know each other better.

Please share:

- Your name
- The organization you work with
- Your interests/ experience in the Sacramento system
- Summer plans you're most excited about

Today's Agenda

01

Introduction
to Project

02

Expert Panel
Framing

03

Open Discussion
with Panelists

04

Lunch

05

Modeling
Overview

06

Small Group
Discussions

07

Report-Outs &
Key Takeaways

08

Collaboration
Opportunities

01

Introduction to the Project

Credit: Mark Clark

Desired outcomes for today

- Identify *challenges and opportunities* associated with an Environmental Water Manager (EWM).
- Develop common understanding of the *state of the science* of environmental storage and flows, including related modeling efforts.
- Discuss *insights, datasets, and tools* that could shape or inform pilot modeling.
- *Refine questions* for this project, including those that modeling of EWM could help answer or explore.
- Identify *research needs beyond* the scope of this project.
- Initiate an external *group of advisors* to support the project.

02

Expert Panel Framing

Our Panelists

**Rene
Henery,**
Trout
Unlimited

**Kristal
Davis-
Fadtke,**
CA Dept.
of Fish &
Wildlife

**Kevin
Thielen,**
Bureau of
Reclamation

Jay Ziegler,
State Water
Resources
Control
Board

**Jeffrey
Mount,**
Public
Policy
Institute
of CA

ENVIRONMENTAL WATER MANAGER WORKSHOP

Kristal Davis Fadtko
Environmental Program Manager

July 18, 2024

WATER STORAGE INVESTMENT PROGRAM

Proposition 1, Chapter 8

- funding for water storage projects that provide a *net* improvement in ecosystem conditions
- 50% of funded public benefits must be ecosystem benefits

WSIP Regulations

- “net improvement” means the gain or enhancement of a resource condition determined by comparing the with- and without-project future conditions less any negative outcomes of a proposed project

CONSIDERATIONS FOR MOVEMENT OF WATER

- Energy costs (lost hydropower, pumping costs)
- O&M costs (not funded under the WSIP)
- Water rights
 - Harm to other water right holders
 - Capacity at export facilities
- Conveyance capacity and priority
- Environmental impacts

SPRING

Mar Apr May June

NET CHANGES IN STORAGE RESULTING FROM PULSE FLOW RELEASE

CHANGES IN VOLUME RESULTING FROM PULSE FLOW RELEASE

SUMMER

Jul Aug Sep

NET CHANGES IN STORAGE RESULTING FROM PULSE FLOW RELEASE

CHANGES IN VOLUME RESULTING FROM PULSE FLOW RELEASE

FALL

Oct Nov Dec

NET CHANGES IN STORAGE RESULTING FROM PULSE FLOW RELEASE

CHANGES IN VOLUME RESULTING FROM PULSE FLOW RELEASE

SITES WSIP ECOSYSTEM BENEFITS

1. Yolo Bypass Pulse Flows for Delta Smelt
 - Colusa Basin Drain capacity
 - Water quality impacts to receiving waters

2. Additional Refuge Water Supply (Incremental Level 4)
 - Capacity at Banks/Jones for south of Delta
 - Exchange to provide water north of Delta

RECLAMATION INVESTMENT IN SITES

Sites Reservoir Project FEIR/EIS: “Exchanges have the potential to assist the CVP in meeting their regulatory obligations and their authorized purposes.” (page 2-88)

Shasta Lake Exchanges may target:

- Cold-water pool maintenance
- Fall-run redd maintenance
- Spring pulse assistance

— BUREAU OF —
RECLAMATION

CVP Background and Modelling

July 18th, 2024

Kevin Thielen, PhD

USBR - California Great Basin Region

Overview

- CVP Background and Challenges
- Key Regulatory Constraints
- Modelling Priorities
- Sites and the CVP

Central Valley Project

- 20 dams, 11 power plants, 500 miles of major canals
- Contracts provide
 - 5 MAF/yr to irrigate ~3 million acres (~1/3 of CA ag land)
 - 600 TAF/yr to urban water users in ~1 million households
- CVPIA dedicates
 - 800 TAF/yr of project yield to fish and wildlife habitat
 - 410 TAF/yr to State and Federal Wildlife Refuges and Wetlands

CVP History

- 1940s– Shasta Dam, Friant Dam, Jones Pumping Plant, and Related Canals
- 1956– Folsom Dam
- 1961– Trinity Division added to import water into the CVP
- 1967– San Luis Unit/State Water Project
- 1968– San Felipe Unit
- 1979– New Melones Dam

CVP Authorized Purposes and Challenges

- Flood Control
- River Regulation
- Fish and Wildlife*
- Water Supply
- Power Generation
- Recreation**

***Prioritized in 1992 by the Central Valley Project Improvement Act**

****Project Recreation Act, 1965**

- Droughts and Floods
- Climate Change
- Aging Infrastructure
- Growing Populations
- Changing Hydropower Markets
- Groundwater and Subsidence
- Invasive Species
- Regulations and Coordination
- Water Quality Compliance
- Endangered Species

CVP Obligations

Upstream Control

- Flow requirements
- Pulse flows
- Temperature requirements
- Delta outflow
 - NDO (D-1641)
 - X2 position

Export Control

- Limit negative flows in Old and Middle River
- Cross channel gate closure criteria
- Export/Inflow Ratio

CVP Obligations

- Coordinated Operations Agreement (1986)
- D-1641
- 2009 Biological Opinions
- 2018 – COA addendum
- 2019 Biological Opinions, 2020 ITP
- Ongoing CVP/Trinity LTO Process
- Future Facilities and Operations
- More!

Modeling Considerations

- Regulatory Requirements:

- D-1641 Requirements
- Minimum required flows below Keswick, below H St., and on Clear Creek

- Deliver to Senior Water Rights

- Settlement Contractors
- Exchange Contractors
- Level 2 Refuges

- ESA Requirements

- Operations Agreements

- CVP Operational Decisions:

- Allocations to Service Contractors
- Reservoir Balancing
- Cold-Water Pool Management
- Delta Water Quality Management

Operational Concerns

- Delta Smelt Summer-Fall Habitat
- Delta-Cross Channel Operations
- OMR Management Season
- Sacramento River Fall Flow Stability and Spring Pulse Flows
- New Melones Stepped Release Plan
- American River Flow Management Standard
- Trinity River Management
- Minimum Flow at Wilkin's Slough
- San Joaquin River Restoration Program
- More!

Sites and the CVP

- CVP Participation up to 25% (360 TAF)
- Improve Water Supply Reliability:
 - Direct releases from Sites to meet current operational and regulatory criteria
 - CVP Obligations met through Sites releases could enhance storage in other CVP reservoirs
- Potential Anadromous Fish Benefits:
 - Shasta cold-water pool enhancement
 - Enhanced reliability of fall flow stability and spring pulse flow releases from Shasta
- Concerns:
 - Only excess flows are diverted to fill Sites, but this may have a future Delta Water Quality Cost
 - CVP is currently undergoing a consultation on a new Long-Term Operations Agreement
 - Sites interaction with other potential storage projects in the works

Thank you!

Kevin Thielen – kthielen@usbr.gov

— BUREAU OF —
RECLAMATION

03

Open Discussion

Questions for panelists and dialogue

Lunch Time

We will come back together at 1:00 p.m.

05

Pilot Modeling Overview

EWM Modeling Perspective for the Sites Project

Many freshwater species in California are endangered or vulnerable to extinction

EWM motivation

Environment as a Constraint

Exhibit 1. Instream Flow Requirements.

Marysville Gage (cfs)

Schedule	OCT		NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	Total Annual Volume (AF)
	1-15	16-31	1-30	1-31	1-31	1-29	1-31	1-15	16-30	1-15	16-30	1-31	1-30	
1	500	500	500	500	500	500	700	1000	1000	2000	2000	1500	500	574000
2	500	500	500	500	500	500	700	1000	800	1000	1000	500	500	420000
3	500	100	100	500	500	500	500	700	700	800	500	500	500	389722
4	400	400	100	500	500	500	500	800	900	800	400	400	400	305944
5	400	400	500	500	500	500	500	500	600	800	400	400	400	334818
6	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	400	400	150	150	300	232165

* Indicated flow represent average volumes for the specified time period. Actual flow may vary from the indicated flow according to established criteria.

* Indicated Schedule 6 flow do not include an additional 30 TAF available from groundwater substitution to be allocated according to established criteria.

Flexible, adaptive management

Steelhead trout

Chinook salmon

EWM concept

'Adaptive governance and flexible management'

Real-time response to ecological conditions

Long-term management of ecological water

Operational transfers

Instream vs Delta priorities

North-of-Delta vs South-of-Delta priorities

EWM core actions

Prioritize ecosystem and species needs at the *time of consideration*

Assess capacity to quickly and efficiently convey water to support those needs; *on-time*, right amount/frequency

Evaluate anticipated vs. realized biological outcomes and environmental responses

Assess opportunities to achieve multiple benefits for multiple ecosystem values

Use the best available science for assessing uncertainty and tradeoffs

EWM pilot modeling → potential

What are the benefits (and costs) associated with real-time management of dedicated (17.6%) environmental storage space, conveyance, and supplies under varying decision-making frameworks?

Pilot

EWM pilot modeling → potential

What are the benefits (and costs) associated with real-time management of dedicated (17.6%) environmental storage space, conveyance, and supplies under varying decision-making frameworks?

Pilot

How could the EWM become more actively engaged in the CA water system, and how would this impact tradeoffs and synergies between environmental and other water users?

Potential

EWM concept → modeling

An adequate modeling framework *must*:

- Capture the plausible range of state-aware EWM actions
- Capture plausible impacts on the ecological outcomes of interest
- Elucidate key tradeoffs (and uncertainty therein) at spatiotemporal scales relevant to the proposed EWM decision making process

A pilot study with this modeling framework *should*:

- Identify key challenges/constraints in the EWM concept
- Identify potential adaptive management practices or reimagining of regulatory guidelines to address these challenges/constraints
- Highlight the potential benefit of emerging capabilities
 - *Ex.: What is the benefit of more flexible management of instream flow requirements based on real time ecological monitoring?*

Potential benefits/challenges of a Sites EWM

Potential benefits/challenges of a Sites EWM

Ecological impacts for water dependent flora and fauna

Potential benefits/challenges of a Sites EWM

Tradeoffs?
Synergies?

Objectives of EWM Pilot Modeling Effort

- 1 Understand drivers of water resource availability and operational value of an Environmental Water Manager
- 2 Components for pilot modeling – clarify information needs, candidate decisions, and strategies for adaptive operations
- 3 Clarify opportunities and gaps in using available modeling frameworks to evaluate the EWM role

knowledge

problem
perceptions

Problem framing: XLRM framework

**X: exogenous
uncertainties**

Uncertain water availability due to climate change

Climate change

X: exogenous uncertainties

Uncertain land use changes in the region

Climate change

**X: exogenous
uncertainties**

Land use change

Uncertainty in extreme droughts and floods

X: exogenous uncertainties

Climate change

Droughts and Floods

Land use change

Uncertainty in extreme droughts and floods

Climate change

Droughts and Floods

X: exogenous uncertainties

Land use change

Ecological uncertainty

Decision making actions

Water releases to and from Sites reservoir

Decisions available to EWM

Method 1: Flows into Sites

Method 2: Flows into Sites

Flows from Sites

Two different
methods

Decision making actions

Cooperative operation between state, federal and local agencies

Decisions available to EWM

— BUREAU OF —
RECLAMATION

CALIFORNIA DEPARTMENT OF
WATER RESOURCES

Water releases to and
from Sites reservoir

Potential avenues of coordination

Operational transfers

Instream vs Delta priorities

North-of-Delta vs South-of-Delta priorities

SPA & USBR, 2023

How to evaluate EWM decisions?

M: metrics

What is success
in environmental
water
management?

EFT example

Key species indicators

	Focal Species & Habitats	Ecological Objectives	Performance Indicators
Sacramento River	Fremont cottonwood	Maximize areas available for riparian initiation, and rates of initiation success at individual index sites.	FC1 Cottonwood seedling initiation index FC2 Risk of scour after successful initiation
	Bank swallow	Maximize availability of suitable nesting habitat	BASW1 Suitable habitat potential (bank length, m) BASW2 Risk of inundation and bank sloughing during nesting
	Western pond turtle habitat, mainstem Sacramento River	Maximize availability of habitat for foraging, basking, and predator avoidance	LWD1 Index of old vegetation recruited to Sacramento River (ha)
	Green sturgeon	Maximize quality of habitat for egg incubation	GS1 Egg-to-larvae survival (proportion)
	Chinook salmon	Maximize quality of habitat for adult spawning	CS1 Area suitable spawning habitat (000s ft ²)
	Steelhead trout	Maximize quality of habitat for egg incubation	CS3 Thermal egg-to-fry survival (proportion) CS5 Redd scour (scour days) CS6 Redd dewatering (proportion)
		Maximize availability and quality of habitat for juvenile rearing	CS2 Area suitable rearing habitat (000s ft ²) CS4 Juvenile stranding (index)

Performance of alternatives

Focal species	Performance indicator	Action Alternatives vs. Existing Conditions			
		NAA (comparison 1)	Alt A (comparison 2)	Alt B (comparison 4)	Alt C (comparison 6)
Green Sturgeon	Egg temperature preferences (GS1)	ni (+1)	+ (+6)	+ (+8)	+ (+8)
Steelhead	Spawning WUA (ST1)	ni (+/- 0)	ni (+2)	ni (+2)	ni (+2)
	Thermal egg mortality (ST3)	ni (+/-0)	ni (+/-0)	ni (+/-0)	ni (+/-0)
	Redd Dewatering (ST6)	ni (+/-0)	+ (+5)	+ (+6)	+ (+5)
	Redd Scour (ST5)	ni (+/-0)	ni (+/-0)	ni (+/-0)	ni (+/-0)
	Juvenile Stranding (ST4)	ni (+/-0)	- (-6)	- (-4)	- (-7)
	Rearing WUA (ST2)	ni (-3)	+ (+5)	+ (+5)	+ (+5)
Fall Chinook	Spawning WUA (CH1)	ni (+2)	ni (-2)	ni (-2)	- (-5)
	Thermal egg mortality (CH3)	ni (+1)	ni (+3)	ni (+1)	ni (+3)
	Redd Dewatering (CH6)	ni (+/-0)	+ (+4)	ni (+2)	+ (+4)
	Redd Scour (CH5)	ni (+/-0)	ni (+/-0)	ni (-1)	ni (-1)
	Juvenile Stranding (CH4)	ni (+/-0)	ni (-3)	- (-4)	- (-4)
	Rearing WUA (CH2)	ni (+/-0)	+ (+7)	+ (+7)	+ (+7)

Defining metrics for different sectors

Theme	Stressor	Metric
Environment	Natural Hazards	Water Supply Exposure
	Climate Change	Climate Risks to Water Supply: Snowpack-dependence of Water Supply
		Climate Risks to Water Supply: Percent of Water Supply at Risk from Sea Level Rise
		Climate Impacts of Water Supply: Reliance on Non-Renewable Energy Sources
	Sensitive Species	Sensitive Species Constraints on Supply Operations
	Watershed Health	Freshwater Ecosystems: Native Fish and Frog Populations
Stream Water Quality: Impaired Waterbodies		
Watershed Condition: Proportion of Land in a Pervious Condition		
Supply	Supply Reliability	Portfolio Strength: Source Vulnerability
		Incidence of Unplanned Mandatory Delivery Cutbacks
		Future Need for Additional Supplies
	Groundwater Supply	Declining Water Levels
	Source Water Quality	Surface Water: Drinking Water Source Water Quality Impairment
Groundwater: Groundwater Quality Impairment		
Demand	Urban Demand	Residential Indoor Water Use
		Urban Outdoor Water Use
		Urban Water Demand: Future Use Trend
	Agricultural Demand	Acreage and Use Trends
Finance	Finance & Investment	Debt Coverage Ratio
		Days of Working Capital
		System Renewal/Replacement Rate

Balancing performance across sectors

Fish
Population

Water
supply

Ecology

....and many others

What models and how to integrate?

Water Resource Integrated Modeling System (WRIMS)

R: Relations

California Food-Energy-Water System (CALFEWS)

WQRRS Water Quality for River-Reservoir Systems

Water Balance Model

Operation of Reservoirs in California (ORCA)

What models and how to integrate?

Sacramento – San Joaquin river basin model (SSJRB)

Coupled model frameworks

Reclamation Temperature Model

Delta Simulation Model II (DSM2)

System water quality modeling (HEC-5Q)

XLRM Framework

Classification of models based on applicability

Water allocation and operations

Operation of Reservoirs in California (ORCA)

California Food-Energy-Water System (CALFEWS)

Water Resource Integrated Modeling System (WRIMS)

Sacramento - San Joaquin river basin model (SSJRB)

Water quality and ecological models

Water quality for river reservoir systems (WQRRS)

System water quality modeling (HEC-5Q)

Delta Simulation Model II (DSM2)

Reclamation Temperature Model

Ecological Flow Tool

Thanks!

References

- Alexander, C. A. D., Robinson, D. C. E., & Poulsen, F. (2014). *Application of the Ecological Flows Tool to Complement Water Planning Efforts in the Delta & Sacramento River: Multi-Species Effects Analysis & Ecological Flow Criteria* (p. 228). The Nature Conservancy.
- Loucks, D. P., & Van Beek, E. (2017). *Water Resource Systems Planning and Management*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-44234-1>
- Null, S., Mount, J., Gray, B., Dybala, K., Sencan, G., Sturrock, A., Thompson, B., & Zeff, H. (2022). *Storing water for the environment* (p. 36). Public Policy Institute of California.
- Sites Project Authority, & Bureau of Reclamation. (2023). *Sites Reservoir Project: Final Environmental Impact Report/Environmental Impact Statement* (2001112009; p. 1997). Sites Project Authority and Bureau of Reclamation.
- Cloern, J.E., Davis, F.W., Grantham, T., Grenier, L., Harder, J., Kuwayama, Y., Moyle, P., Schwartz, M.W., Whipple, A. and Yarnell, S., 2019. A Path Forward for California's Freshwater Ecosystems.

06

Small Group Discussions

Discuss questions to explore considerations for:

1 Environmental Water Management

2 Modeling Efforts

Small Groups

Group 1

Molly Daniels
Will Anderson
Rene Henery
Jennifer Harder
Andrew Ayres

Group 2

Robyn Grimm
Jay Ziegler
Wyatt Arnold
Jon Herman

Group 3

Sai Veena Sunkara
Jeff Mount
Kevin Thielen
Andrew Schwartz
Romain Maendly

Group 4

Zach Brodeur
Greg Young
David Okita
Josue Medellin Azuara
HB Zeff

#1

Questions for Small Groups

What are the benefits of explicitly allocating storage for environmental flows in the Sacramento system?

#1

Questions for Small Groups

If you were an environmental water manager, what knowledge/ resources would you use/need?

#1

Questions for Small Groups

What are the challenges associated with establishing an operationally effective environmental water manager within the Sacramento system?

Stretch Break

We will come back together at 3 p.m.

#2

Questions for Small Groups

What are the highest priorities and evaluation metrics for modeling the tradeoffs and synergies associated with an Environmental Water Manager (EWM)?

#2

Questions for Small Groups

What are key regulatory, operational and natural constraints and uncertainties for a modeling effort to capture?

#2

Questions for Small Groups

What are important resources (datasets, tools, models, etc.) and candidate collaboration opportunities for modeling the implications of EWM decision frameworks and scenarios?

Report-outs from Small Group Discussions

Hear high-level summaries of small group discussions considering the environmental water manager needs and modeling effort

Thanks!

We appreciate your time and insights shared today.

CREDITS: This presentation template was created by [Slidesgo](#), and includes icons by [Flaticon](#) and infographics & images by [Freepik](#)

